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Research Article

**HOW SELF-EFFICACY INFLUENCES KNOWLEDGE
SHARING AND ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP
BEHAVIOR: A SOCIAL APPROACH FORM EMPLOYEES OF
PHARMACEUTICAL COMPANIES**¹Zubair Akram, ²Muhammad Naeem Shahid, ³Zafar Iqbal, ⁴Hafiza Rabia Akram,¹School of Management and Economics, Beijing Institute of Technology, South-Zhongguancun Street, Beijing 100081, PR China, zubairakram91@yahoo.com²Assistant Professor, The University of Faisalabad³Lecturer, Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Kotli⁴Public Health Service Management, The First Affiliated Hospital, China Medical University, Shenyang 110001, Liaoning, China hafiza_ra@outlook.com**Abstract:**

This study focuses on how self-efficacy plays an important role as moderator between knowledge sharing and organizational citizenship behavior. The target population of this study comprises sales and operations department of pharmaceutical companies operating in Islamabad, Pakistan and the employees of pharmaceutical companies were taken as unit of analysis. The data was collected from 350 employees through a well-established questionnaire by random sampling technique. The study used Cronbach's alpha, correlation test, multiple regression and ANOVA test to find consistency of data, the type of relationship between variables, effectiveness of self-efficacy between relationship of knowledge sharing & organizational citizenship behavior and difference between knowledge sharing intensity among the different departments respectively. The results established strong correlation between knowledge sharing and organizational citizenship behavior. The study confirmed that self-efficacy strongly and positively affects the association of organizational citizenship behaviour and knowledge sharing.

Keywords: Knowledge Management; Organizational Citizenship Behavior; Self-efficacy; Pharmaceutical Companies

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Knowledge is defined by (1) as “Knowledge is a fluid mix of framed experience, values, contextual information, and expert insight that provides a framework for evaluating and incorporating new experiences and information. It originates in the minds of knowers. In organizations, it often becomes embedded not only in documents or repositories but also in organizational routines, processes, practices and norms”. In the era of globalization, if knowledge is maintained efficiently, it has significant competitive advantage for any business. Knowledge specialists are appointed to handle business rivalry by providing encouragement and assistance in decision making and developing business strategies (2). (3) endorsed the importance of strategic management both in academic and practical concerns and considering the war of talent; moved the focus to knowledge-based view rather than resource-based view of the organizations. They argued that the knowledge-based view of organizations have been considered to be the most significant resource of an organization enabling it to achieve and sustain long-term competitive advantage. The notion is that a resource becomes a strategic resource if it is valuable, rare, and hard to copy. Thus, many research scholars have emphasized on the insinuation of knowledge-based view of organizations and mulled over it as a strategic resource (4; 3) and organizations are strained to invest in knowledge management and the main reason behind this is to build the knowledge capability that facilitates the flow of knowledge and information within the organization through effective knowledge management (5). One of the best ways of knowledge management is knowledge sharing where individuals exchange ideas through discussions which further helps in formulating new ideas as examined by (6). (7) explains “Reciprocal causation” as a situation where one segment relies upon the working of the other up to a certain extent. The focal of knowledge management is on the belief that organizational performance can only be achieved through developing the resources of their potential employees (8). Many research scholars including (9); (10); (11); (12) stipulated that knowledge management steers organizations about how to enthrall experts’ knowledge that resides within the organization and formalize as well as disseminate it for being capable of reuse by other employees of the organization for fulfilling the identical causes in order to achieve shared objectives for enhanced organizational performance. (13) remarks that organizational behaviour is an employee’s willingness to collaborate with honesty and provide genuine volunteer service without expecting any

extra incentive and keeping in mind the advancement of the organization. (14) have reflected that “Innovative and spontaneous behaviour” by an employee outside the assigned role is recognized as Organizational citizenship behaviour.

This study addresses the fact that many employees do not participate in knowledge sharing as they are afraid of losing power and value. It is conducted to determine how self-efficacy moderates such behaviour. The study is significant because an environment of knowledge sharing and significant positive Organization Citizen Behaviour is important for any organization to be successful and have competitive advantage.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Knowledge Management

Research on knowledge management is increasing in literature because of its realization and recognition in setting up strategic directions for organizations. (1) argued that there are several perspectives which contribute to the field of knowledge management through which the discipline of knowledge management can be observed such as knowledge engineering, artificial intelligence, cognitive science, social science, philosophy, information science, economics, and management (15). Though a lot of disciplines describe knowledge management and contribute in this field, thus there are a number of definitions based on the different philosophies (16). (17) acknowledged that because of the lack of a mutual agreement on knowledge management, knowledge management definition revolves around two core concepts:

1. Knowledge as a Thing
2. Knowledge as a Process

2.2. Knowledge Sharing

(18; 19) have noticed that the exchange of ideas, experience, tactical knowledge, expertise between employees of an organization is knowledge sharing. The key aspects of knowledge sharing are knowledge donating and collecting. Organizations where knowledge sharing is implemented, individual learning is interactive and fast and organizational performance improves due to long term creativity (20). (21) perceived that Knowledge sharing is influenced by many factors-Self-reliance and confidence, organizational strategy, team work, communication, commitment, nature of knowledge etc. Knowledge sharing has competitive advantage for an organization and provides employees with better employment interpretation and acknowledgement (22; 23).

2.3. Self-Efficacy

(24) have observed that Self-efficacy influences individual performance, decision making capabilities during tasks, individual behaviour, assessment of rules and regulations. Self-efficacy should be encouraged during career development as it improves academics and behaviour. Individuals with self-efficacy share knowledge comfortably without stress and need not be forced to do so (25).

(7) have remarked that employees with self-efficacy approach individual goals with technique and understanding and this further helps in knowledge sharing. Self-efficacy of an individual improves participation in volunteering for tasks not required by their job description (26). (27) has concluded that

Self-efficacy has a positive effect on organization citizenship behaviour.

2.4. Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

(28) deduced that Organizational Citizenship Behaviour is participation and flexibility in the work environment which is not very likely to be rewarded formally. According to (29), Organizational Citizenship Behaviour has five dimensions:

- Courtesy
- Sportsmanship
- Civic virtue
- Altruism
- Conscientiousness

Figure #1

Hypothesis 1

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) has significant positive effect on Knowledge Sharing (KS).

2.5. Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)

(30; 31) have analyzed that the Theory of Reasoned Action is a model of social psychology which explains motivation and expectation behind an individual's behaviour. Knowledge Sharing based on intention and type of knowledge is affected by an individual's social standards and progressive attitude (32; 33). Correlation analysis shows that relation between organizational citizenship behaviour and knowledge sharing is positive (34). (35) has identified that there is positive association of knowledge sharing and organizational citizenship behaviour. When essential knowledge is shared with an employee, there is a significant improvement in work behaviour and participation and it also provides a sense of empowerment to the employee, as noticed by (36; 34).

Hypothesis 2

Relationship between Knowledge Sharing (KS) and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) is positively moderated by self-efficacy (SE).

Figure #2

2.6. Social Cognitive Theory

This theory claims that individuals react to environmental influence and effectively try to interpret the situation for more information. (37) has stated that in a system influenced by collective cooperation, individuals work for their own inspiration and progress. (38) in their study have found that Social Cognitive Theory emphasizes an individual's belief in his/her capability of effectively finishing tasks and objectives. (39) has defined an 'agent' as someone who intentionally influences working and life conditions of an individual. Social Cognitive Theory has four major procedures for acknowledging any goal;

- Self-evaluation
- Self-efficacy
- Self-reaction
- Self-observation

Social Cognitive Theory is an 'agent' with respect to advancement and adjustment within an organization. (40; 41), High levels of efficacy in members of a team has better chances of them participating in sharing information required for the achieving goals of the task at hand. (42) in their study have concluded that Faculty members of an organization shares more knowledge and information if they are more confident of their own capabilities. Positive relationship between self-efficacy and organization citizenship behaviour has been evaluated many studies, as noted by (43; 44; 45; 46). A study by (47) showed that there is not any observable relation between self-efficacy and organizational citizenship behaviour.

Figure #3

2.7. Knowledge Sharing Intensity

(48) have discussed in their study that Knowledge intensity defines the degree of the reliability of an organization on knowledge characteristics for competitive advantage. (49; 50; 51) also observed that Knowledge intensive organizations are highly dependent on the work of knowledge. Robertson, Scarbough & Swan (2003) have remarked that often, survival of knowledge intensive organizations depends on its capacity of activating and organizing knowledge.

Hypothesis 3

Different Departments have different levels of knowledge intensity.

(48) have expressed that knowledge intensity shows the reliance upon knowledge and shows it as merit. According to (49) in Knowledge intensive organizations dependence is always placed on work of knowledge. Not every activity within an organization will thrust upon knowledge alone nor their ability to collect and utilize knowledge to survive was observed by Robertson, Scarbough & Swan (2003).

3. MATERIAL & METHODOLOGY:

The present research has considered 'Knowledge sharing' as an independent variable. 'Organizational citizenship behavior' is taken as a dependent variable and 'self-efficacy' has been seen as a moderating variable. Primary data was collected by use of questionnaire tool. Questionnaires were equally given to sales and operations departments of different pharmaceutical companies. The questionnaire can be divided into various segments. Demographics such as sex, age, designation etc. form the first segment. The dimensions are measured using five point likert

scale ranging between strongly disagree and strongly agree.

The present study has used simple random sampling method to identify the 2 departments/wings out of the total 19 departments. To gather data, non-probability convenience sampling methods was utilized by the researcher.

Sales and operations are the two department identified for data gathering. The variables have the following reliability (a) knowledge sharing - 0.731(12 items); (b) organizational citizenship behaviour - 0.770(12 items); and self-efficacy - 0.753 (8 items).

Table# 1

Variables	Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Knowledge sharing (KS)	12	0.731
Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB)	12	0.770
Self-efficacy (SE)	8	0.753

To check the similarity or discrepancies in the variable 'knowledge sharing' within the identified departments, One-way ANOVA is being utilized. Turkey Test will be applied if there are differences seen on the same variable. Moderator analysis is used to understand the relationship of the two variables on the third variable. This relationship may be found between continuous independent variable and continuous dependent variable. To identify the moderating effect, multiple regressions are being utilized. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 24.0 is used to analyze the data gathered from all 350 respondents of the two departments.

3.1. Research objectives

The study objectives are;

- To examine and understand the association among the two variables Knowledge sharing and Organization citizenship behaviour.
- To inspect the action of self-efficacy in association among Knowledge sharing and Organization citizenship behavior.

3.2. Data analysis and research findings

In total, 350 respondents from the two departments were identified and questionnaire was instituted. In first section respondents were asked to provide general information about their gender, age, study specialization, and job designation in the company.

In case of data about age, majority of respondents about 87% are male and female participants were just 13%. This is not biased towards one gender as the study has been conducted in Pakistan where job market especially supervisory and managerial positions, is male dominant. Hence the target respondents were mostly male. As for as the information about age is concern, about 50% respondent were aged between 26 ~ 35 years, age of about 20% were ranged between 36~45 years, while 13% of respondent has age above 46 years. There are also some young respondents which were about 17%, aged below 25 years.

With respect to study background of respondents 60% of selected samples have background of management studies and 35% were studied pharmacy in their educational career. While just 5% were general studies like arts and other social studies. As the main purpose of this study is to explore the role and significance brand portfolio strategy in enhancing firm's performance related to pharmaceutical business operating in Pakistan, hence, to get more comprehension and the true picture, it was necessary to investigate educational background of the target respondents.

To achieve study objectives the data were collected from top management of pharmaceutical companies. Therefore, 50% respondents were working as marketing managers and 40% was working as product manager. While just 10% of respondents

having designation as assistant marketing managers in different pharmaceutical companies.

To get the more valuable and comprehensive data, maximum effort has been made by the researcher to avoid any type of data biasness.

Normality of data was checked through different techniques. Skewness and kurtosis value were ensured well in accepted range of -1.96 to +1.96. Shapiro-Wilk's test was also showing significant values. Linear relationship among study variable was in straight regression line as it is check by using probability plot. Durbin Watson statistics was applied to check data normality and the results values were

well in range 1.5 to 2.5, which confirms that there is no data auto-correlation problem in the data. To check the relationship among study variables, correlation analysis were also conducted which shows correlation values (0.637 to 0.689) and P-value is less than 0.001.

3.3. Testing of Hypotheses (H1)

As we have assumed that knowledge sharing (KS) has significant and positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), the results ($t = 16.367$, $\beta = 0.688$ & $P < 0.05$) in co-efficient table are also depict that KS is significant predictor of OCB.

Table# 2

Model	Standardized Coefficient	R square	T	Sig.
	Beta			
1 (Constant)			6.991	.000
Knowledge sharing	.688	.470	16.367	.000

3.4. Moderating Test

Table# 3

Model	Standardized Coefficients B	R square	T	Sig.
1(Constant)			15.514	.000
KSMEAN	.686	.470	16.272	.000
2(Constant)			13.172	.000
SEMEAN	.425	.578	8.689	.000
3(Constant)			12.637	.000
KScentralize×SE centralize	.009	.680	.244	.029

Multiple regression statistics are used to understand the outcome of using self-efficacy as moderator to test association among 'knowledge sharing' and 'organizational citizenship behavior'. The results reveals positive and significant impact of knowledge sharing on OCB ($\beta = 0.686$, $t = 16.272$, $P < 0.005$). The impact of self-efficacy is also positive and significance on OCB as results depict ($\beta = 0.425$, $t = 8.689$, $P < 0.05$). The regression results regarding centralized value of knowledge sharing and self-efficacy with respect to organizational citizenship behavior are also having significant values ($\beta = 0.009$, $t = 0.244$, $P < 0.05$). Therefore we can

conclude that the independent variable is significant predictor of dependent variable. Furthermore, there is also significant role and effect of mediating/moderating variable between the independent and dependent variable so all the study hypotheses H1, H2, and H3 are accepted.

4. CONCLUSION:

"Knowledge sharing" and "organization citizenship behavior" have strong and positive correlation is the one of the most important finding of this study. As 'Knowledge sharing' increases 'organization citizenship behaviour' is also found to be increasing.

The study has also found out that self-efficacy can take part as a moderator to investigate the relationship among the variables 'Knowledge sharing' and 'organization citizenship behaviour'. The effect of self-efficacy on both the variables has been negative. Also, it is found that knowledge sharing has insignificant variance among the four departments.

5. LIMITATIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

The difficulty to generalize the findings of the study is the core of the limitations since four departments were selected for the study randomly. Because of inability of being impartial among the various grades of employees, there may be some negative impact on the study. This can be seen as another limitation of the study. High grade employees may not have responded accurately because of the work load and pressure, inability to perceive the nature of questions due to lower education level. There may be biased or negative answers because of multiple reasons. The study can be applied for more departments as future research is one of the recommendations. Other organizations such as universities, hospitals etc. may be identified for further research.

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